

“HUMAN RIGHTS” A TOOL OF WESTERN POWER, A POST-COLONIAL CRITIQUE. COMPARATIVE STUDY OF PALESTINE AND UKRAINE CASES

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ABSTRACT

The discourse surrounding “Universal Human Rights” as enshrined in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights is subjected to post-colonial deconstruction. It refers that the regime upholds western dominance rather than a vehicle for global justice. This paper advances the central thesis that how human rights framework operates as a form of neo imperial control that is used by powerful states to secure geopolitical, economic and cultural influence under the guise of moral responsibility. The study traces how the UDHR emerged from enlightenment-era thought and reflected Western philosophies while it excluded non-Western perspectives such as African, Islamic and Chinese traditions. Drawing on the works of Edward Said, Frantz Fanon and Noam Chomsky, it highlights how human rights discourse is applied selectively to justify interventions or sanctions against rivals like Russia and China while how it overlooked violations such as Israel and Saudi Arabia. Using the contrasting cases of Palestine and Ukraine, the paper exposes the double standard in practice. The western response to the Russia-Ukraine conflict through sanctions, military aid and international outrage shows a sharp contrast to decades of silence and unconditional support for Israel despite the ongoing human rights violations in Palestine. This imbalance reveals that the inconsistency in human rights enforcement is not accidental but deliberate as it holds a system that is designed to serve western interests behind the moral façade of universalism.

Keywords: Cultural Relativism, Post-Colonial Critique, Universal Human Rights, Neo-Imperialism, Orientalism, Eurocentrism

INTRODUCTION

Human rights are those rights which belong to an individual or group of individuals just for being human. Every individual is born free, and he is equal in dignity and rights. Human rights are comprised of set of norms which govern the treatment of individuals, states and on an ethical basis, which society considers to be fundamental to a peaceful life. These norms are enshrined into national and international legal system which specifies the procedure to the duty bearer.

According to these mechanisms duty-bearers are held accountable. The philosophy of “Human Rights” is based on ethics and justice. They are built on the idea of altruism and cooperative human nature. Human rights are considered to universal, and nobody should be deprived of them on the base of sex, race and religion. The notion of universalized individual can be seen in the writing of Immanuel Kant, John Locke and Rousseau. The idea of these philosophers was

magnified in the American Declaration of Independence (1776) and in the French Declaration of Rights of Men and Citizens (1789). According to Legal Positivist Human Rights were created by the conventions and norms. They are of the view that 'natural rights' are derived from natural or divine order which are immutable and absolute rights are deduced from 'Positive law' which is recognized and accepted through legal and political process that results in treaty, law and declaration. Before becoming part of legal system, Human Rights' claim emerged due to the suffering of people and when they subjected to oppression and cruelties. They are based on moral sentiments and religious and cultural system. The NCOs emerged in the world as a social movement following the mistreatment of prisoners and exploitation of workers and slaves. Colonialism, apartheid, ethnic cleansing and exclusion of women from the mainstream politics and economic system also invoked social sentiments in the world against the violation of human rights. The idea of sovereignty came from the Peace of Westphalia (1648). According to the treaty, no other state or group of state can intervene in the domestic affairs of any state. How a state treats its public and individuals was considered as a domestic and internal matter of state. But after the time, this concept was changed and after creation of United Nations Organization (UNO) in 1945, states pledged to comply with Human Rights and to promote the value of it.

No doubt, the historical evolution of Human Rights reflects the Western World, and it has become synonym with Western Political development and its values and norms. All the evolutionary process of Human Rights e.g., Magna Carta, the English petition of Rights (1627), the United States Constitution (1787) and then lastly Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR) took place in the Western World. After the end of First World War in 1945, Western World started promoting Human Rights and pledged to adopt their foreign policy which could comply with UDHR. They claimed that the UDHR is to be universal and should be adopted by the states and nations throughout the World. Imposing own values and norms reflects the intensions of dominance throughout the World. In the diverse

world every nation and religion has its own norms, culture and values. How can Western World deny the culture and values of other nations while imposing their own values and culture? In the theory the Human Rights which are incorporated in the UDHR are universal, but many nations have their own set of human rights. In Asia there are certain practices and norms such as idea of family over the individual is contrary to the idea of Western construct of human rights.

Western Power has been used as a tool of Western Power to achieve their national interest. During the Cold War, USA and its allies used to malign Soviet Union as a violator of human rights and the Soviet Union was portrayed as a violator of Human Rights. In this regard Western Power has double standard. Saudi Arabia has been violating the Human Rights but no Western Power neither its media highlighted the human rights issue, but China has been accused of violating the human rights of Uyghurs. Pressure is inserted against the rival state of Western Power through Amnesty International, Human Rights Watch etc. India is involved in serious human rights violations, but US government never denounced India as it has geopolitical interests with India. At Present time US and its Western allies are ignoring the despotic policies of Israel against the Palestine but human rights pressure has been intensified on Putin in order to halt him.

Research Questions

- 1) Is notion of Human rights a western Centric?
- 2) How do Western powers use Human Rights as a tool of their foreign policy?

LITERATURE REVIEW

In the book 'Black Skin, White Masks' Frantz Fanon wrote that colonization had psychological effects on both colonizer and colonized. He asserted that the indigenous population developed a sense of self which is defined by the colonial master through the discourse and prevailing ideas. On the other the colonizers developed sense of superiority when they interacted with the colonized nations. To deal with these native people try best to look white as possible in order

to deal with psychological inadequacy. For this they try to adopt the religious and cultural values, their language while rejecting their own culture and values. This sense of insecurity ignites violence within colonized nations. The sense of inadequacy and inferiority is the form of self-assertion. Violence is likely to erupt against its own natives as natives realize that they cannot become completely white. Fanon argues that the instance of violence is generated through the colonial system. Because natives become rivals of each other and fail to turn against the colonial master. Frantz Fanon described that there are stages in which national culture of colonized nation is formed. In the first stage colonized nations or natives tried to rewrite their history and culture. In this stage they seek to conform their culture to the colonizer by discarding their own history and culture. In the second stage natives realize that their culture can never be similar to the colonizer and they acknowledge that they cannot be truly white or white enough for the colonizer to treat them equally. Nevertheless, in the third stage the natives are anti-colonial in the wake of critical analysis of their own culture. Third stage gives rise to cultural nationalism. It leads to xenophobia and intolerance in society. But national cultural has very limited value to prevail and compete with the overwhelming assault of colonizer. Frantz Fanon also argued that this cultural nationalism did not ensure the remedy of working and oppressed class. He further explained after getting Independence, power struggle between colonizer and natives does not disappear but it remerged between the native elite and the commoners of the postcolonial society. The intensity of manipulation, exploitation and suppression continues in the same way.

In the book "Orientalism" Edward Said introduced the concept of Orientalism that is force which shaped Western academic scholarship, cultural imagination, academic scholarship, cultural imagination and scholarship linked with space which he called as the Orient. Orientalism is a pattern of thought which is made on ontological and epistemological distinction and this distinction promotes the supremacy of West (Occident) over the Orient. Orient is defined as the people of the Orient and as an

adjective it can be defined as the Oriental landscape, attitudes, culture and literature. The Orient is comprised of present geographical territories of Asia mainly Middle East, Far East and Near East. Historically, the Orient has been deemed and considered as opposite and contested with the West which was comprised of Europe in the past and the later USA explored the hierarchical relationship between the West and the East. This book explained that under the dominance of West the production of knowledge continues to influence and promote Western intervention in the domestic affairs of the Middle East and the rest of Asia. According to Edward Said the existence and development of any culture requires other's culture to be diminished or compel competitors to adopt their culture. So, Europe attempted to construct self-image and for this they created Middle East as the ultimate 'other'. Edward Said highlighted how intellectual and political activities occurred between Occident and the Orient. Western World studied Islam under the umbrella of science (observation and objective reality) and they juxtaposed between their culture and values and Islamic norms and values. They understood Islam according to their way and then propagated Islamic values as stereotypes and they are deemed as sinful, barbarians and inferiors to Europeans.

Stephen Kinzer writes in his article "End Human Rights Imperialism" that human rights violations in the world are so pervasive and shocking that it is present need to rethink and remake the movement of human rights. Human rights were magnified by the idealist at global level for the purpose of making this world peaceful, however recently it has become a tool of new form of imperialism. Imperial power intends to overthrow the government of poor states. Through this they (imperial powers) want to build and foster military interventions all around the globe. They want to undermine all the governments who are trying to uplift their people from poverty. The reason is simple they do not comply with the intellectual discourse of elite intelligentsia of imperial powers. Not only Amnesty International but they have other tools in shape of Human Rights Watch and Reporters Without Borders to the Carr Centre of Human Rights at Harvard, through which they

propagate their anti-genocide movement which serves their interests. All promotes human rights' view which is pervaded by modern Western ideas which they call 'universal'. Practically instead of saving lives, it causes more deaths, repression and human disaster. World remembered the civil war of Nigeria (1960-1970). Western Powers were supposed to mobilize world opinion and international organizations to defend Biafra rebels and to prevent the genocide according to them which Nigeria would perpetrate against the rebels. Protest started all around the global against the government of Nigeria which prolonged the war and caused countless deaths. Finally, when the rebels were defeated, the genocide never happened.

Noam Chomsky in his book "How the World Works" and his earlier essays like the Washington Connection and Third world Fascism and Manufacturing consent complemented the post-colonial theorists such as Fanon and Said by talking about economic and institutional perspective. He argued how United States and its allies use 'human rights' discourse selectively for strategic and economic domination. He highlighted how West targets rival states by invoking human rights but stays silent when allies commit equal abuse. He calls it 'the moral facade of empire'.

Chomsky talked about institutional structure of domination by highlighting how corporate and state power intertwine to maintain a stable global capitalist system. Media conglomerates and political elites share mutual interests, and human rights become a way to justify interventions, sanctions or trade restrictions in order to protect western investments and geopolitical influence. He called out the West by highlighting the use of 'free markets' and 'liberal democracy' in human rights rhetoric. This is the language that imperial powers use to hide a material reality of control. Western powers use economic structures to create dependence in the Global South. He used the analogy of 'worthy victims' and 'unworthy victims', how West gives sympathy and coverage to its allies (worthy victims) and ignores those who harmed its allies (unworthy victims). Universalism claimed by UDHR mirrors the universalism of capitalism.

WHAT ARE HUMAN RIGHTS?

According to the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR), human rights are universal and related to human dignity. In UDHR there are five categories of human rights such as civil, social, political and cultural rights. Subsequently these rights are classified into first, second and third generation rights. It does not mean that these rights are confined in one category but most of the rights fall under more than one category. For example, the right of expression comes under both political as well civil rights.

Civil and political rights fall in first-generation rights. These rights emerged in Europe during seventeenth and eighteenth century, and these were linked with political concerns. During that era, Europe had been undergoing political, social and economic changes. Europe had come out of the Era of Darkness, and scientific revolution was taking place. Europe made progress in the field of science and social sciences. European Philosophers played a vital role in the nourishment of these rights through their writings. John Locke, Voltaire, Rousseau and many others' philosophy contributed to making progress regarding these rights. There was a huge shift in social, political and economic structure of Europe. Feudalism was being revoked, and capitalism was taking its place. Monarchy was about to end, and democracy was taking the place of it. Civil and political rights are encompassed with personal liberty and protecting individuals from the despotic authority of the state. At Present time the detail of Civil and Political rights is embedded in the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR). 'Civil and Political Rights contend that every national and the people have right of self-determination and to choose to develop their culture and set up their political structure. Every party to the covenant should ensure the respect and dignity of every individual within their territory without their color, sex, race, opinion, language, religion and their national origin etc. Every state should undertake such steps through the constitution and legislation in order to ensure these rights, so that they may not be jeopardized.

Social, economic and cultural rights fall in second generation rights. They are related to how people

live together, interact together and the right to work to fulfill their basic needs and requirements. These rights are centered on the discourse of equality, access to economic and social opportunities which are pre-requisite for the nourishment of any individual. In this regard, social rights are those rights which are required to participate and deliver in the field of social life. These rights include right of education, and the right to make family. Furthermore, in this category, those rights which are included in civil rights but also come under this shadow of social rights such as freedom from discrimination, privacy and recreation. Economic rights are those rights which are necessary for the preservation of human dignity. These includes right to work, retain living standard, minimum wages and equal opportunities of job without the discrimination of race, sex and nationality. It also includes the preservation of private property as well as the right to do trade and business. It is responsibility to every state to fulfill the basic requirements of its people which are related to economic perspective. For the state, it is imperative to reduce poverty within the state. Cultural rights are those which specify the identity of specific group or nation. Cultural are often less get mainstream attention. However, these rights are incorporated in the UDHR. In the realm of cultural rights every individual or group of individuals has right to participate in the cultural life of community. They are supposed to enjoy their culture, confess and promote their culture. They can enjoy art and historical heritage. In multi-ethnic states, minorities are subjected to suppression. In this regard, that state should take measures for the purpose of preserving their culture.

Finally, comes the category of 'Solidarity Rights based on third generation Rights. The list of human rights is not static, but it keeps on changing by the time and it undergoes evolutions. The new discourse develops regarding human rights and therefore it is necessary to include new development in the discourse. New changes and development in world and events are important factors in the birth of these rights. From the world solidarity illustrates that these rights are based on the collectiveness of society and nations. In this category we can put those rights such as

sustainable development, peace and healthy environment. There are many contemporary issues in the world which are impacting negatively whole, so it also requires collective efforts in order to contain the humanitarian disaster. For example, world is on the verge of disaster of climate change and environmental degradation. So, it requires the recognition of new rights such as right of clean environment.

POST-COLONIAL CRITIQUE ON THE DISCOURSE OF "UNIVERSALISM "OF UDHR

According to post-colonial theory, the creation of UDHR had resulted in the wake of different events and philosophical and political development in Europe and in the USA. In 1215 the most important political event in UK underscored human rights and that was Magna Carta where King was compelled to grant certain civil and political rights to the people. Then American Independence 1776 became a major hallmark in context of granting rights to individuals and they are incorporated in the constitution of America. Subsequently French Declaration of rights of men and citizen (1789) also paved the way in field of granting certain rights to individuals and people. These major developments had their own political and economic foundation. The industrialization and rise of capitalism played major role in substantiating these rights. These changes shifted Europe from monarchy to democratic setup. However, rest of the world was not experiencing such political and political changes. So, they have different views regarding human rights. UDHR became the essence for subsequent international human rights regimes, treaties and covenant and was born on the ashes and bloodshed perpetrated by European Powers and the United States of America. Western Powers fought each other in the shape of the First World War and Second World War and both sides committed crimes against the humanity, but UDHR became tool of winners against the losers. Nazi Germans and Italian Fascists were demonized and the Allied powers especially USA, UK and France were being demonstrated as champions of human rights. The creation of UDHR happened after just three years

of unleashing nuclear weapons by USA on the Japan's cities __ Nagasaki and Hiroshima. Nuclear attack by USA killed almost 1.4 innocent civilians of Japan.

During the time when UDHR was declared UNO had been ruled by Western Power and only 58 states had privilege of being member of United Nations Organizations (UNO) and only 48 members of UNO had voted in the favor of UDHR and other 10 members abstained to give their votes. Ironically at that time, two third states of whole world were absent in the process of declaration of human rights and pathetic was that those two-third states were still colonized by those states who drafted UDHR. The commission of UDHR was led by the wife of Roosevelt and first lady of US at that time Eleanor Roosevelt. On the other hand, there were only two non-westerner members but they both got their education from the US, and they were soaked with Western political thoughts. These arguments illustrate clearly that 'Universalism' of Human Rights declared by Western powers is fabricated notion and it was spread intentionally.

Article 2 of UDHR states that Everyone is entitled to all the rights and freedom without the any discrimination of any kind based on race, color, sex, language, religion, political differences, national, property, birth or other status. Moreover, no distinction shall be made based on the political, jurisdiction or international status to the country or territory to which a person or individual belongs, whether it be independent, trust, non-self-governing or under any other limitation of sovereignty. But antithetical, the UDHR did not renounce the colonization as it was severe violation of human rights in the colonized territories. The reason was obvious that UDHR was under those who colonized those territories.

The evolution of human rights in Europe is entirely different with other regions such as Africa, China and Middle East. In Africa the society is based on the tribalism and the African society bolsters tribal and communal structure instead of individualism. The political philosophy of Africa can be summarized as "I exist because we are, and because of we are I am". So, this idea of African philosophy substantiates kinship and tribal

structure as compared to the western discourse of individual and his/her rights. The family structure of Africa is unique with the rest of the world as there is terminology for aunt and cousin there. Aunt is called as older mother or younger mother. Similarly, cousins are equivalent to brother and sister. The social life of Africa is hierarchical in nature, which is totally opposite to Western social life. If we talk about the Islam, then we will also find the sense of community as Islamic philosophy is based on the Tauheed (oneness) of God. It explains that all the mankind is family of God Almighty and being part of this everyone has some rights as well as some obligations. In Islam human are entitled by rights just because he/she is human and the source related to it is Quran. Islamic perspective of human rights did not undergo evolution or struggle of centuries. Similarly Chinese society has different notion regarding human rights, and they give more importance on obligations and responsibility of individuals than the rights. But in UDHR the different perspectives of different cultures were overlooked, and the entire focus was on the Western-centric interpretation of human rights.

In the view of Enlightenment Universalism and its post-colonial critique, Enlightenment thinkers considered Europe to be 'civilized' and justified colonization. Emmanuel Kant's Enlightenment Universalism has been criticized for its framework that universalizes the European subjectivity but excludes the subaltern. Contemporary Southeast Asian and post-colonial critics questions the Enlightenment based constructs to whether they are culturally translatable or repackage colonial hierarchies. On the other hand, Condorcet Enlightenment philosophy Was criticized. It was questioned whether his belief in universal rights universal or was it just shaped by colonial thinking? He was criticized for assuming that only 'civilized' societies could exercise self-rule and about denying sovereignty.

Feminist scholars and activists have criticized the human rights framework for its gender blindness. It marginalized women's life experiences in the sphere of family, sexuality, reproduction and domestic violence. We see how human rights discourse institutionalized through Universal Declaration of human rights (UDHR) continues

to shape the priorities of global rights regimes. Historically, the UDHR (1948) and the International Covenants of 1966 were shaped by Westphalian sovereignty, patriarchal social norms and liberal legalism. Civil and political rights were prioritized but rights specific to women were neglected. There is an emphasis on individual autonomy but there is a lack of attention to relational interdependence which fails to address the gendered nature of human vulnerability. Post colonial feminists such as Chandra Talpade Mohanty and Gayatri Spivak that criticized Kant's Enlightenment Universalism argue that Western human rights activism portrays women in the Global South as victims in needing rescue. The question is raised whether global human rights regimes truly serve women or instead solidify existing geopolitical asymmetries?

'HUMAN RIGHTS' AS A TOOL OF NEO-IMPERIALISM

There is nexus between knowledge and power. The prevailing ideas all over the world are set up by powerful actors to maintain and preserve their dominance over others. The notion of human rights is the one of the tools of powerful states which serves their interests. By using 'human rights' as their tool Western Powers promote their culture all around the globe and compels other to adopt others to adapt themselves according to their culture. West raises human rights issues in the developing states as their cultural values promote gender inequality and racial discrimination. So, people in the developing states start denouncing their own culture and values and start adapting themselves which Western Powers want to achieve their interest in shape of dominance of their culture. We can see such example in the South world where there has been large number of feminist movement inspired by the Western family system and cultural values and they start challenging their own values and culture. Edmund Burke was a British scholar, and his philosophy was based on the conservatism. He favored British colonialism, and he was the view that Western civilized world should colonize barbarians to make them civilized. This nation still exists in the foreign policy of Western Powers.

Through the 'Human Rights' as tool, Western Powers invade the South World. In 2001 and 2003 respectively, the USA invaded Afghanistan, and it used same terminologies __ we are going to send our troops to promote democracy and freedom of individuals. Though it was severe breach of sovereignty of these mentioned above states and US is responsible for tens of thousands of civilians' casualties, it was never quelled or renounced by the liberal international institutions. In the cloak of 'human rights' the USA followed its vested interest.

The standard of 'human rights' enshrined in UDHR promotes individualism, democracy and right to free trade economy. The idea of individualism, democracy and free trade economy promotes capitalism in whole world. All the neo-liberalism institutions work under the influence and hegemony of the USA and its Western allies. The notion which Western powers have been promoting that free trade economy will render prosperity of whole mankind. But the economic statistics are totally opposite to it. The economic gap between developing states and the Western states is being increased day by day. Through multinational companies, West is exploiting natural resources from the developing state in the name of Foreign Direct Investment (FDI). There was a report in BBC that the main ingredient of chocolate is extracted from the Africa, but African countries get only one percent of the profit and rest of 99 percent of profit goes in the hand of Western countries. This indicates how Western Powers preserve their economic hegemony in the mask of 'Human Rights'

CASE STUDY OF PALESTINE AND UKRAINE ISSUES

Western powers have been using 'human rights' issue as propaganda to demonize their powers. During the cold war they used to denounce USSR and labelled it a despotic where there is no value and importance for human rights. At present time US is using it as a tool against any state which is not suitable to national interests of the USA and its key allies. It is evident that Iran is portrayed as a theocratic state. On the other hand, the questions of human rights violation are not raised against the Kingdom of Saudi Arabic despite

severe violations of human rights. Since KSA has been a staunch ally of US, no questions of human rights – suppressing minorities and the murder of journalist – is raised. One side they consider themselves as proponent of democracy and human rights. On the other hand, Western powers have been involved in toppling democratic states such as in Chile, Guatemala, El Salvador etc. Recently after the Arab Spring in 2011, Muhammad Morsi became first elected head of state of Egypt. Since he opposed Western interest, his government was overthrown, and the new dictator Khalid el-Sisi was launched.

Recently Ukraine crisis has exposed the dual standard and hypocrisy of universal values regarding human rights. When Russia invaded in the end of 2021, Western states invoked international humanitarian law started imposing severe sanctions on Russia. Western states welcomed refugees from the Ukraine and supported the resistance and cheered up the arm struggle of Ukraine. Social media was flooded with the hashtag of Ukraine invasion by Russia and people started asking for banning Russia from different cultural events in the world. The invasion was portrayed as serious violation of international law and the Western politicians and diplomats asked for the support against the Russia in order to promote their propaganda.

On the other hand, the people of Palestine have been subjected to the suppression and violence of Israel since the creation of Israel. Since last 17 years around 17 thousand Palestinians are killed by Israel. Israel is involved in the apartheid against Palestine. It is expanding its territories, and it has occupied Western Banks, Golan Heights etc. For the Palestinians there is different law, and they are subjected to discrimination. Their homes are demolished by Israel. But the USA and other Western countries never imposed sanctions Israel. It has been called the only partner of West in Middle East which shares the Western liberal ideas. The casualties and violations of human rights committed by Israel are more than Ukraine's casualties but whole West raised the voice and supported Ukraine.

Western powers have always had double standards over Palestine. The atrocities happened to the people of Palestine and due to the national

interests of the West with Israel, it has been quiet. Western nations were questioned by Asian media that these imperial powers showed 'swift' support to Ukraine but ignored Palestinians. The question comes to mind. Are human rights incorporated in UDHR just symbolic or are they catering to the interests of the Western powers? Deputy Prime Minister Ahmed Zahid Hamidi addressed lawmakers in the parliament, "Why are these two different approaches? For instance, in the Ukraine crisis, the Western powers swiftly provided support to Kyiv. Unfortunately, when it comes to Palestine, it is entirely disregarded." This shows that human rights rhetoric is being questioned as it should be and West is being unapologetic about it.¹⁸

Western politicians and their so called 'free media' have always made themselves to look at as the Pioneers of human rights and now they are keeping mum about the atrocities going on in Palestine for the past 75 years. Israel has always violated the rights of Palestinian people. Humanitarian law and international human rights law have been violated by the occupation categorized as: Unlawful killings, forced displacement, abusive detentions, the closure of the Gaza Strip and the development of settlements. Despite Israel's bombings on the shattered lands of Gaza Strip it has cut off food, fuel, medicines and other necessary supplies showing the violation of the 4th Geneva convention. After everything, Israel has refused to budge and has bombed the Rafah crossing that connects the conclave to Egypt. How unapologetically cruel can one be?

Global community has condemned the attacks. Arab and African nations condemned the genocide. United Nations Human Rights Council, Arab League, United Nations Middle East peace envoy, China and Russia have called out the Israeli cruelty and the commission of genocide. But US and European countries have done nothing as they pose themselves to be the savior of humanity and human rights. US has continued its aid to Israel which is comprised of 158 billion dollars since World War 2. US condemned the attacks by Hamas 'terrorists' on October 7 and called them 'unprovoked'. What is provocation? Not the settlers storming Al-Aqsa

Mosque, apparently. Not the 248 Palestinians killed by Israeli forces between January 1 and 4 October of 2023. Not the denial of Palestinian human rights.

Western media has always played a decisive role in the conflicts to shape the perception of the world according to its own terms. West put its attention where its interests are concerned. It even considers the conflict if happens in West as something foreign, shows shock that it happened in 'civilized' Europe rather than 'Middle East' or developing countries. These statements show West's assumption of superiority and racism, as if violence is expected in Arab and Muslim countries and not when it strikes Europeans. West has double moral standards.

Palestine resistance is depicted as unprovoked attacks and Russia's war on Ukraine has different moral terms, narrated as aggression, occupation and a violation of international law. Ukrainian resistance was considered heroic, but Palestinians were criminalized. Media coverage varied so much regarding the conflict zones. Positive news content like release of hostages and ceasefire deals were seen in the coverage of Israel and negative approach of news coverage from Gaza such as terrorist attacks, disasters, protests etc. It's clear and evident that West has always used human rights discourse to serve and cater for its own interest in ensuring global dominance.

CONCLUSION

This paper attempts to deconstruct the notion of universalism of Human Rights as Western World promotes it. Through the post-colonial theory, the other perspectives to see the prevalent discourse of human rights have been revealed. There is strong relation between knowledge and power. In this context the stronger intends to preserve its hegemony through the knowledge which prevails all over society or global. Similarly, Western States use the idea of "Human Rights" to keep intact through hegemony and the dominance. Since the Second World War, international order was created by the Western Power, so it has been serving the interest of them. By analysing "Human Rights" in different perspective, one can clearly see the difference of reality and rhetoric of universalism of human rights incorporated in UDHR.

¹⁸<https://www.aa.com.tr/en/middle-east/malaysia-questions-double-standards-of-global-community-on-palestine/>

¹⁹<https://pressxpress.org/2023/10/17/wests-silence-in-the-face-of-israels-brutality-the-painful-double-standards/>

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